

CATALYZING ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON METACOGNITIVE AND EXPLICIT APPROACHES IN TEACHING CHEMISTRY

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Catalyzing Academic Achievement: A Comparative Study on Metacognitive and Explicit Approaches in Teaching Chemistry

Anamarie G. Valdez,*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study focused on the effectiveness of the Metacognitive and Explicit Approaches on the improvement of the Grade 9 students' academic achievement in Chemistry based on their pre-test and post-test scores. The respondents of the study were composed of 80 Grade 9 students with the same level of achievements in science. This study employed the Experimental Research Design, specifically, the Pre-test / Post-test Explicit approach design. With this design, the researcher identified two whole classes of the Grade 9 students for the school year 2014-2015. These classes were randomly selected as to form one (1) experimental group and one (1) explicit approach. To determine if there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental groups and explicit approach, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Tukey – Kramer Multiple Comparison Test, t – test and Analysis of Covariance of unequal n (ANCOVA) were used. The results showed that the levels of the student's academic achievement in their pre-test, and post–test scores using the two approaches were “Beginning”. On the other hand, the students' ability in understanding chemistry concepts was underperforming or struggling in learning. Hence, the result of the post-test revealed that students under Metacognitive Approach was extremely significant. Moreover, students performed well in the post-test. Further, the students performed better in the post-test than in the pre-test. Students have gained higher means as compared to those of the Explicit Approach. Hence, the Metacognitive Approach in teaching greatly affected or influenced the students' academic achievement. Generally, the use of metacognitive approach indicates that students can easily acquire knowledge, skills, and insights and these would also mean that better learning and greater participation can easily take place.

Keywords: *Philippines, catalyzing academic achievement, chemistry, explicit approach, metacognitive approach*

Introduction

Learning instructions nowadays come in different styles and forms. Educators are now investigating new teaching and learning methods that aim to improve the quality of education and the quality of citizens produced by schools. One of the new methods in learning instruction today is the modular approach wherein teacher intervention is minimal. This style of teaching and learning is student-centered since the student has to learn everything in the module through his efforts and pace.

This method deviates from the conventional classroom situation wherein a teacher presents the lesson and the students just listen to learn the concepts presented. This gives the researcher an interest to do a study on how effective is this modular method in the teaching of computational sciences like chemistry and what are the factors affecting the student's achievement and retention of concepts in this kind of method. A poor chemistry foundation in secondary school will jeopardize any future effort to enhance comprehension of the subject.

In this rapidly and constantly changing world, the challenge of the teaching milieu is to help students develop skills, abilities, and cognitive domains that will not become outdated. Metacognitive strategies are essential for the twenty-first century because they enable students to cope successfully with new situations.

The researcher conducted this study to guide students on how to use their cognitive knowledge in a deeper sense so they can apply it in future studies and may use it in preparation for the higher demand in the field of education. Chemistry problems can be solved using a variety of techniques. This research endeavors to help the students to use different strategies in solving problems, not only in Chemistry but, also in other fields that include mathematical operations and deeper understanding to the problem.

Constructivism refers to a synthesis of multiple theories diffused into one form. It is the assimilation of both behaviorist and cognitive ideals. According to Jean Piaget, the learner's knowledge is built with the help of the learner's activities that help him to make discoveries in his mind. Thus, the mental activity of the learner is emphasized and the teacher needs to create a situation whereby the learner associates his previous knowledge (Moore, 2004). Moreover, Vygotsky believes in social constructivism and that the construction of knowledge is socially oriented (Cole & Wertsch, 2002). Moore (2004) believes that learning happens with the interaction with the environment.

Constructivist principles strongly support the use of metacognitive strategies in chemistry education by emphasizing active learning, self-regulation, and deep understanding rather than rote memorization. Here's how constructivist principles align with metacognition. Constructivism posits that learners actively construct knowledge rather than passively receive it (Piaget, 1972; Vygotsky, 1978). Metacognitive strategies, such as self-explanation and reflection, encourage students to engage deeply with chemistry concepts, enhancing comprehension and retention (Flavell, 1979).

Further, constructivist principle that supports metacognitive strategies is scaffolding, where learners receive support that helps them progress through their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) (Vygotsky, 1978). In the chemistry classroom, scaffolding can take the form of peer discussions, teacher feedback, and collaborative problem-solving activities that help students refine their thinking and develop self-regulation skills. Studies by Brown et al. (1989) show that scaffolding encourages learners to reflect on their learning process and make adjustments, fostering metacognitive awareness. Such interactions enable students to gain insights into their thinking and learning patterns, which, in turn, enhances their ability to engage in higher-order cognitive tasks, such as hypothesis testing and data interpretation in chemistry.

Additionally, deep conceptual understanding rather than surface-level memorization is a central tenet of constructivism. This focus on meaningful learning aligns with metacognitive strategies that encourage students to connect new knowledge with prior experiences and understanding (Chi, 2009). For instance, concept mapping and self-explanation techniques help students build connections between new chemical knowledge and what they already know, enhancing retention and application in different contexts. In a study by Karpicke and Roediger (2008), the authors demonstrate how active learning techniques, such as retrieval practice and self-testing, lead to better long-term retention, a finding that supports the role of metacognitive strategies in fostering meaningful learning experiences.

Recent research further emphasizes the benefits of integrating metacognitive strategies in chemistry education. A study by Dunlosky et al. (2013) highlights the effectiveness of strategies such as self-questioning and distributed practice, both of which encourage students to monitor their understanding over time and adjust their learning approaches. Similarly, Harris et al. (2021) found that metacognitive strategies improved not only student achievement but also their ability to transfer knowledge across different contexts in science education, including chemistry. By reflecting on their learning, students are better able to apply chemical concepts in novel situations, which is essential for success in both academic and real-world chemistry problem-solving scenarios.

Moreover, constructivist principles provide a strong theoretical foundation for incorporating metacognitive strategies into chemistry education. These strategies not only promote active engagement and deep understanding but also foster the development of self-regulated learners who can apply their knowledge flexibly and independently. By aligning metacognition with constructivist approaches, educators can help students build stronger problem-solving skills and a deeper understanding of chemistry that extends beyond memorization. In this study, the researcher assumes that the use of these learning modules affects the academic achievement of the students.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of the Metacognitive Approach and the Explicit Approach in the enhancement of academic achievement among Grade 9 students in the chemistry subject. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the levels of students' achievement in their pre-test and post-test scores using:
 - 1.1. metacognitive approach; and
 - 1.2. explicit approach?
2. Is there a significant difference among the pre-test scores of the students using the different teaching approaches?
3. Is there a significant difference among the post-test scores of the students using the different teaching approaches?
4. Is there a significant difference between students' achievement in the pre-test and the post-test under the two approaches?
5. How do students' achievements differ as influenced by the two (2) methods of teaching?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed the Experimental Research Design, specifically, the Pre-test / Post-test Explicit approach design. With this design, the researcher identified two whole classes of Grade 9 students. These classes were randomly selected to form one (1) experimental group and one (1) explicit approach. To purposely control the teacher-factor effect, the researcher handled the three classes; the first section of Grade Nine used the Metacognitive process and the second section used the Explicit Approach.

These two (2) classes were given a diagnostic test as their pretest and, at the end of each module, the respondents were given their posttest. The performance of these groups was presented, analyzed, and evaluated using statistical tools appropriate for the study.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were composed of 80 Grade 9 students of Kapingkong National High School who were randomly selected. The students were grouped based on their first grading grades in Science. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

	<i>No. of Subjects</i>
Group A	40
Group B	40
Total	80

Instrument

This study developed a module that was patterned after that of the K to 12 curriculum. The ideas and concepts were gathered from different textbooks and references. The modules covered the topics; Electronic structures of matter, Chemical Bonding, and Carbon Compounds and Moles. This was evaluated by Chemistry experts using the questionnaires adopted from the study of Lumaque, (2011) and Lambino, (2012). The modules were evaluated in terms of mechanics, objectives, contents, relevance, innovativeness, appeal and conformity with standards. The acceptability of the learning modules was determined using a five point scale with appropriate interpretations and descriptive ratings. The result of validation by the experts went through face validation by the panel.

To determine the academic achievement of the students, the researcher constructed a 50-item test that was used as a pre-test and post-test questionnaire. The researcher-made test was validated and Kuder – Richardson Formula 20 was employed to ensure the reliability of the test.

Procedure

A teacher-made pre-test was administered to the experimental groups to equate the two experimental groups.

The class was divided into two groups. The first group and second groups were composed of forty (40) students each with a total of 80 students. Before the start of the experiment, the researcher made a 100-item test and was subjected to validation by a group of twenty-five (25) randomly selected fourth-year students of SKSU Science Laboratory High School. After the modification of the results, the researcher found out that most of the test items were difficult and had a low discriminating index. To make it more valid and reliable the researcher did the second validation, took a 60-item test, and was subjected to validation by a group of twenty (20) randomly selected fourth-year students of SKSU Science Laboratory High School.

The experimental groups were isolated to prevent contamination of learning materials and activities. Equal conditions for both groups were equated. The same teacher taught the subject. After the third quarter of experimentation, the researcher administered the researcher-made posttest to both groups to determine the academic achievement of the students.

For the purpose of presenting and interpreting the validity and reliability of the results of the instruments, the Kuder – Richardson Formula (rxx) was used. The researcher used the Index of Difficulty and Index of Discrimination to eliminate very easy items and very difficult ones. Data collection was conducted on the third quarter of the school year, 2014 – 2015.

Data Analysis

This study used the mean of the students' pre-test and post-test scores to determine the academic performance of the experimental and explicit approaches.

To determine if there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental groups and explicit approach, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Tukey – Kramer Multiple Comparison Test, t – test and Analysis of Covariance of unequal n (ANCOVA) were used.

Results and Discussion

This section focused on the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from Kapingkong National High School, Division of Sultan Kudarat in response to the problem of the study. This would give a true picture on how the respondents assessed the approaches in teaching Chemistry and the academic achievement of the Grade Nine (9) students of Kapingkong National High school.

Students' Academic Achievement

Table 1 provides the Pre – test and Post – test mean score's level of the respondents' academic achievement under the three teaching approaches. Further, the corresponding mean was rated with the equivalent percentage as shown in scale above.

Table 1.

	<i>Pre – test Mean</i>	<i>Equivalent (%)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Post-test Mean</i>	<i>Equivalent (%)</i>	<i>Description</i>
Metacognitive Approach	15.20	30.40	Beginning	19.10	38.20	Beginning
Explicit Approach	13.13	26.26	Beginning	14.26	28.52	Beginning

Table 1 shows the level of the students' achievement in Pre-test and Post-test using the two approaches as method in teaching and learning experiences. Comparing the Pre-test scores of the students under Metacognitive Approach got a mean score of 15.20 which is equivalent to 30.40 percent. The result shows that students under Metacognitive Approach belong to the level of "Beginning". This implies that the students are struggling in the acquisition of knowledge or have not acquired the knowledge, skills and understanding.

Similarly, the explicit approach attained a mean of 13.13 in the Pre-test, equivalent to 26.26 percent. It also shows that the student's achievement in the Pre-test is in the level of "Beginning". The coefficient of variations 26.18 %, and 24.90% for Metacognitive

Approach, and Explicit approach respectively, indicate that all of the students' achievement is widely varied. It further explains that, at the start of the experiment, it further means that there are students who got very high scores and there are those who got very low scores.

In the study of Pulmones, (2008), various metacognitive activities were designed adhering, as much as possible, to constructivist principles. These activities were designed for students to inductively construct their knowledge either from given empirical evidence or by letting them use their prior knowledge as they develop their understanding of the different chemical concepts.

The students' achievement in the Post-test using the three approaches shows that at the end of the experiment, Metacognitive Approach got a mean score of 19.10 which is equivalent to 38.20 percent. The result shows that students under Metacognitive Approach belong to the level of "Beginning". In the same way, the explicit approach attained a mean of 14.26 in Post-test, equivalent to 28.52 percent. It shows that the students' achievement in the Post – test is at the level of "Beginning". The coefficient of variations for Metacognitive Approach is 20.42 %, while the Explicit approach has 21.60%.

Further, the indicated findings evidently reveal that students' achievement is widely varied. As Abdullah, (2012) remarked teaching approaches and materials had greatly influenced the learning performance of the students in experimental group as confirmed by a significant mean gain score difference in their academic performance compared to that of the explicit approach in the post – test.

Table 2 below shows the results of the Analysis on Comparison of the Pre-test.

Table 2. Results of the Analysis on Comparison of the Pre-test SKSU, 2015

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>Fcomputed</i>	<i>Probability</i>
between	87.44	2	43.72	3.61	0.03
within	1391.1	115	12.10		
Total	1478.60	117			

α=0.05 of significance

The analysis yielded a test value of $F = 3.61$ with a probability of 0.03 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. The results reveal that the difference between students' achievement in the pre-test is not attributed to chance. It means that, among the three groups of respondents, there is, at least, one group that performed well in the pre-test.

Table 3. Results of the Analysis on Comparison of the Post-test SKSU, 2015

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>Fcomputed</i>	<i>Probability</i>
between	602.72	2	301.36	18.45	< 0.0001
within	1878.60	115	16.34		
Total	2481.30	117	14.26		

α=0.05 of significance

The analysis yielded a test value of $F = 18.45$ with a probability of <0.0001 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. The results reveal that the significant difference between students' achievement in post-test is not attributed to chance. It also means that, among the three groups of respondents, there is, at least, one group that performed best in the post-test.

Comparing the pre-test and post-test of students in Metacognitive approach, yielded a value of $t = 5.04$ with a probability less than 0.0001, which means that the difference between the pre-test and post – test of the students using the Metacognitive Approach is extremely significant. There is enough evidence to claim that the student had a higher achievement in post-test than in pre-test. This implies that the student performed well in the post-test.

Further, Mason and Nadalon (2005) found that overall students' metacognitive competence significantly correlated with their achievement in subjects. Similarly, Coutinho (2006) concluded that students with good metacognition tend to be successful students. Students with poor metacognition tend to perform poorly.

Furthermore, the findings show that students' academic achievement was greatly affected after the given intervention.

Findings show that the pre-test and post-test of students in the Explicit approach, yielded a value of $t = 1.55$ with a probability less than 0.1245, which means that the difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students using the traditional approach is not significant at 0.05 level of significance. There is enough evidence to claim that students who were exposed to the traditional way of teaching had a lower achievement in their pre-test and their post-test. This implies that students obtained lower mean gain, thus, experiencing the least progress in their academic achievement. The findings are affirmed in the study of Abdullah (2012), Solano (2007) when she emphasized that students subjected to the traditional approach obtained a smaller mean gain score compared to the students exposed to a variety of modern exploratory activities.

In the next table, a result of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) between the mean scores of Experimental groups and Explicit approach is presented. To determine how students' achievements differed as influenced by the two methods of teaching, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used.

The table below presents the results of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Table 4. *Results of the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). SKSU, 2015*

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>FComputed</i>	<i>F Critical value</i>
between	87.44	2	263.43	16.16	3.074
within	1391.1	115	16.30		
Total	1478.60	117			

α=0.05 of significance

The analysis yielded a computed $F = 16.16$ which is greater than the critical value 3.074 at 0.05 level of significance. There is enough evidence to claim that variations among students' achievement are attributed to methods of teaching used in the delivery of lessons. These imply that the interventions of the researcher employed in the method of teaching Chemistry for Grade 9 students affected students' achievement. Additionally, there is a high probability that improvement of the students' achievement from the pre – test to post – test was triggered by the methods of teaching. The results validate the arguments that, though at the start of the experiment students in Metacognitive Approach may likely have better achievement than those students in explicit approach under the tradition approach, both Metacognitive Approach gained higher means compared to the Explicit approach. These confirm that the method of teaching caused change on student's achievement.

Moreover, Lambino (2012) found out that teaching in a traditional way also improved the performance of the controlled group, but not as high as the achievement of the experimental group. Additionally, lesser skills are learned by the students in the controlled group due to spoon-feeding strategy while in the experimental group, the students' work independently using the module.

Conclusions

The level of student's academic achievement in their pre-test and post-test scores are low under the two approaches. This implies that the students are struggling in the acquisition of knowledge or have not acquired the knowledge, skills, and understanding.

There were no changes or improvements in pre-test scores between the Metacognitive Approach and the Explicit Approach. On the other hand, the pre-test scores of students under the Metacognitive Approach were greatly improved from that of the Explicit Approach.

It implies that the students in the Experimental group may likely have the same achievement as that of the Explicit approach in the pre-test. Hence, there was no significant difference in the post-test scores of the Metacognitive Approach. The post-test scores of those under the Explicit Approach were highly significant in difference under the Metacognitive Approach.

Findings reveal that there was a highly significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of students exposed to the Metacognitive Approach. Moreover, the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of students is also extremely significant. On the other hand, there was no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of students under the Explicit Approach

The results of the Analysis of Covariance reveal that the methods of teaching greatly affected or influenced the academic achievement of students at a 0.05 level of significance. Furthermore, the interventions given by the teacher who taught the subject were effective.

Generally, the use of various teaching approaches indicates that students can easily acquire knowledge, skills, and insights and these would also mean that better learning and greater participation can easily take place.

The academic achievement of the students may be given emphasis on the basis of the grading system. The grading system should therefore be given consideration based on the achievement of the students.

Modular Approaches in teaching and learning should be practiced to develop the knowledge, skills, and attitude of the students, to motivate them, and to make them enjoy learning. It will also help schools with a high rate of absentees and drop-outs.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Anamarie G. Valdez

Sultan Kudarat State University – Philippines